

Implementation Network DCC (IN DCC)

3 November 2020, Marjolein Drent (UT)
Co-chair IN DCC with Jeroen Rombouts (EUR)

DCC 's Network

- aimed at supporting each other in DCC developments (peer consultation)
- participation by representatives from the thematic DCCs as to translate the wishes of the researchers into services provided by the thematic DCCs, and conversely the contact with the local DCCs can make it easier for the services and toolings from the thematic DCCs to be seen and used by the researchers
- to form the connection to SURF, the SURF RDM “regiegroep”

Some facts

started in June 2020

36 members from 13 universities, 5 UMC's, 4 on behalf of HBO, and also DANS, DTL, eScience

2 meetings, one with NWO on call

2 chairs (Jeroen Rombouts and Marjolein Drent)

Coming meetings: November on Governance: three members (Leiden, Groningen, HBO DCC) will explain and discuss the way they are planning to organize the governance of their DCC's

Plans near future

IN DCC for next two years supported by LCRDM/SURF

November on governance, and start of inventory relevant themes

- E.g. training

- Fair data/software

- Research Software Engineers

- Domain specific Datasteward support

January inventory of more relevant themes and how to work together